

EDUCATIONAL RESOURCE UTILIZATION: IMPLICATIONS FOR EDUCATIONAL MANAGERS

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ABSTRACT: Education is the best and largest enterprise all over the world and the only tool for societal advancement, social mobilization, economic development, political survival and effective national development of any country. Investment in education is vital for the promotion of economic growth and national development. Educational institutions including schools are established and managed essentially to achieve certain stated goals and objectives, which cannot be achieved without entrusting a large amount of responsibility for human resources towards ensuring the success of such institutions. In the school system, part of the integral pre-requisites to be put in place towards the actualization of the educational goal and objectives requires the adequate provision of resources, maximum utilization and appropriate management of education resources to avoid wastages and improve the quality of the teaching-learning process in the academic environment. This paper examined the concept of educational resources utilization, classification of educational resources, education resources and educational manager's roles, the challenges of educational resource utilization, roles and attributes of educational managers on resource utilization as well as the implications of effective resource utilization. The paper concluded that the success of the school depends among others on effective school administration with good manager, proper time management in the school system, allocation of ample financial resources to school, perfect interrelationship with community and ingenious utilization of resources in the school system. The paper suggested that Government should organize Seminars to equip the 21st century school managers with the current techniques for managing school resources.

Keywords: Education, Resources, Utilization, Implications, Funding, Administration, Managers.

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INTRODUCTION

Education is a veritable tool for growth and development of society. It lays foundation for literacy, skills attainment, technological advancement, the ability to harness and manage the natural resources in the environment and functional society. The quality of every society is largely dependent on the quality of its educational system (Ololube, 2017). In the light of the apparent limitations on educational resources, their efficient utilization for the maximum result need not be stressed. Ololube (2017) posited that there has to be administered in any organization as long as an organization consists of people brought together in hierarchical set-up making use of tools, equipment, human and material resources, all in the quest of attaining the goals for which the organization is established. No organization, educational sector inclusive can adequately achieve its objectives without adequate availability and utilization of resources.

According to Ololube (2017) and Usman (2016), educational administration and educational resource refers to all variables which make educational systems function effectively. These variables are essential for the smooth running of every school system and the actualization of educational goals and

objectives. Educational institutions without these resources will not be in existence and if they are, will definitely not function optimally. Educational resources are livewire which sustains the educational system. Resources to education are valuable assets made available in the school system, used in the process of trying to achieve educational goals.

These resources are inputs that make the system functional and direct the development of educational sectors. These resources include raw materials, wealth, or possessions used to achieve educational set goals and objectives whenever they are needed (Chuz-Nyeche, 2014).

Resources such as money, materials, time and human can only be effectively utilized for the realization of educational goals if well managed by leaders, who direct and control the other factors for survival and sustenance of the educational system. Most educational activities are implemented at the direction of a leader. Such leader set rules, design, work systems, goals, and strategies, provide goods and services and supervise quality, and draw up a financial plan and some others.

The managers of the system become the most valuable resource in the education sector. Without human resource, all others will not be utilized and unproductive. Adieme and Asodike (2014) observed that the most important and vital task of management is to motivate the human resource to maximize its performance and achieve corporate success. Nevertheless, educational managers are either employed or appointed to head, direct, control, coordinate, organize and analyses issues in school and ensure slated goals and objectives of the school are implemented. Management involves a type of responsibility aimed at achieving particular ends by applying the available resources (human and material) and ensuring a cohesive and coherent organization in the process (Bratton & Gold, 2012). For education to be effective there should be a manager, that has the requisite skills acquired through experience, knowledge, commitment, patience to achieve set goals. It has been echoed that the most important skills a manager requires are communication skill which enables him to negotiate and work with others to achieve goals and objectives ensuring effective utilization of educational resources.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Educational Resource

Educational resources have gained popularity among educators, administrators and instructional designers, popularizing the idea that digital materials can be designed to permit free reuse in a large range of teaching and learning situations (Hysten, 2007). Educational resources are all the various sources through which institutional gains are produced (Nwabueze in Ebong & Asogike, 2016). Educational resources as observed by Ezekoka (2009) is seen as anything thing use to facilitate, stimulate and simplify the learning process in the classroom. Generally, education resources refer to all human, material, non-material audio-visual school environment and community materials available in an academic environment to facilitate school administration and simplify the teaching-learning process.

They also include other fundamental materials used in the school to make teaching very easy and learning more meaningful and comprehensible to the learners. Education resources cover all those materials human and non-human, drawn or photographed, built manually or electronically operated books and all forms of related materials used in teaching and learning process (FRN, 2014).

Education resources include the teachers in the school, human beings in the community, real objects, specimen or models, chalk and display boards, school buildings and layout, the community at large and other fundamental materials like pencils, pens, exercise books etc. (NOUN, 2009). Education resources are no doubt important in the development of a conducive teaching-learning environment. The use of these resources could give more valuable and powerful direction to the teacher than any personal efforts without the materials. However, no matter how well packaged a school administration or a school system is at any

level of education, without adequate and efficient utilization of the available resources, as well as the accessibility of educational resources, the system will not be able to achieve its desired results (objectives and goals).

Accessibility of education resources makes school management effective and efficient thereby enhancing the output of the education system. The effective school administration is key in achieving education goals that will lead to an efficient instructional process which will in turn yield quality output. Agabi (2010) observed that the resources provided by the Government for the execution of education projects in Nigeria are inadequate and irregular as highlighted by the frequency of industrial actions in the education sector. More so, due to the general level of poverty in the country, the contribution of communities and households to educational provision have been negligible. Consequently, the best alternative is prudence in the use of available resources. This is because when a given level of resources is efficiently utilized, more services are provided through balance usage and adequate maintenance of the available facilities than when inefficiency, on-utilization, under-utilization and overutilization abounds.

According to NOUN (2009), education resources are classified based on their nature, thus the following categories:

- **Material or Physical Resources:** These are the tangible resources that can easily be seen and observed in any institution. The physical resources include the structure, the machines, raw materials, vehicles, and other tools, which can facilitate organizations activities and processes, which directly or indirectly contribute to the achievement of goals.
- **Financial Resources:** Financial resources are important in the school system, however financial management is more important in the system. Although the two (financial resources and financial management) could be used interchangeably; the overall of it is that funds are required for the smooth operations of a school and are regarded as the life-wire of any system. Whereas financial management is the activity of obtaining and effectively utilizing the funds necessary for an efficient course of action. Finance Planning and executing an educational programme cannot be overemphasized because without the available financial resources, the desired human and material resources would be impossible to procure adequate funding contribution to the non-provision of educational facilities talk less the maintenance of such facilities as school building, furniture, laboratory, library, classrooms and so on all of which pose a great challenge to the management of educational facilities and consequently affect quality education deliver It is indeed a more critical facet with which other factors of administrations are created, maintained and sustained.
- **Time Resources:** Time is a unique resource and is considered as one of the scarce resources known to man. Time is the most expensive of all resources due to its non-recoverable nature. Time utilization refers to the proper allocation of time to the various stages and tasks of administrative activities. In a school system, time is managed through the use of a time table. Consequently, time management refers to those apparatus set in place for the organization's effectiveness and in the pursuit of the realization of setting out objectives and goals (Ugwulashi, 2012).
- **Human Resources:** Human resource constitutes a vital vein of any institution. The human resource in the school system includes teachers, support staff in the school, students, parents, community members and a host of other interest and social groups.

Human resources are responsible for planning, organizing, coordinating, controlling, manipulating and maintaining other forms of resources; its administrative and forecasting ability placed it ahead of other forms of resources.

Educational Managers and Utilization of Human Resources

Human resources here refer to teachers, non-academic staff or personnel of any educational institution. This kind of resource is the brain of the school system which is used to achieve educational objectives within a set period of time. These resources enhance the implementation of educational policies because it makes uses of other educational resources. Nwabueze (2016) observed that they are the life-wire of every organization in a given society. Human resources stand as strength in every school system, they are producers, teachers, and the main reason for every school system, without them there will be no students and learning will not take place. They make up the workforce of an educational system in every teaching and learning institutions, this set of people are skilled workers and very important in the planning, teaching, implementation of educational policy made, development scheme, carry out research and community services to keep the system functional (Kaegon, 2011).

The human resource is usually directed by a leading human resources manager (HRM), he as a leader help in placement of different specializations of the human resources, see to the roles and capabilities of who are an integral part of the organization and ensure all these are properly directed to achieve educational goals. The human resource manager who is the leader may be called the principal, ahead of the department, a provost, a vice-chancellor, a headmistress or master. A board chairman, a commission for education or an administrator in a school environment he/she ensures each teacher employed or posted to the school are properly placed in departments and given subjects to be taught based on his or her area of specialization and ensure duties are carried out as stated by the leader. He also directs other human resources in the school system like employees, consultant, part-time personnel, nonacademic staff or any person, with different types of other relationship to the institution/organization and ensures he/she is transparent and honest in his dealings. Educational resources provided by the government must be efficiently utilized to keep school programs running.

Educational Managers and Utilization of Resource Material

Utilization is the degree or extent to which an item has been put into effective use. He identified the various degree of utilization as overutilization, underutilization, non-utilization and optimum or optimum utilization, according to him, non-utilization is when the facilities are not put into use at all, maximum utilization occurs when facilities are put into effective usage in line with the primary objectives. Underutilization occurs when facilities are not used beyond its capacity while optimum utilization occurs when facilities are used for many purposes by the school and members of the public or the community. These degrees of utilization of educational facilities constitute a waste resource and are counterproductive. To ensure that science equipment are not only needed but must be effectively and efficiently utilized to avoid wastage in relation to demand them' hence, utilization of science equipment in secondary school on laboratory exercises are performed routinely or only when the school in preparing for external examination.

In other words, whether the available science equipment is used in the routine teaching and learning process in anticipation of external examination and in the best part of the year the equipment is dumped in the laboratories without utilization. Proper utilization, inspection and supervision are much needed by school administrators in their daily management of educational facilities for quality education delivery in their respective schools. These will minimize the rate at which educational facilities are damaged by both the students and the teachers an as well create instant awareness for school administrators to know any damaged facilities that needed maintenance or replacement .hence this strategy will enhance proper

management of educational facilities for quality education delivery. Material resources are non-human resources used for the achievement of educational aims within a set an.

Okpe (2010) noted that material resources as things which satisfy schools' wants. These resources are consumable which act the hub on which teaching and learning revolve. It is very important to note the place of material resources in the teaching and learning process. They are visible items in physical forms used in impacting and getting knowledge. Also, material resources as infrastructural facilities and finance available for use by the human resources within the organization. For him, it is all necessary equipment tools instructional aides, all physical items available to improve teaching and achieve a successful result. The material resource in education has the main contributions to motivate and make students learn more effectively as learning becomes interested when it is audio and visual that is, the student hears and see what they are taught. Material resources are usable and consumable facilities such as furniture, buildings, textbooks, stationery, chalkboards, equipment, electricity, modern educational electronic gadgets, computers, instructional materials, teaching aids and lots more. All these are tangible in every school sectors in order to achieve educational aims and objectives. Classroom, laboratories, libraries, also should be furnished and equipped to improve stress-free learning and teaching are all important in the achievement of attaining the school goals (Obasi & Asodike, 2014).

Consequently, the material resource has never been sufficient in the educational system and have limited the ability of the school manager to an extent, yet the recent trend has been overpopulated and increase in the demand for education in every state adding with the United Nation's education for all (EFA) project which had contributed to huge increase in the enrolment of people in school. This material resource is not usually enough and not always available at the point of need to match the demand of students of the enrolment explosion. Usually, the increase put pressure on the material resource available in school and the shortage of this available resource. Therefore, the facilities used during learning make understanding of what is taught unforgettable. On this note, the principals which are managers must ensure the provision of all instructional materials in his/her school also must ensure he controls both teachers and students in the usage of these materials provided to ascertain their durability, maintenance effective utilization of those facilities and proper handling of such by those it was meant to be used.

Facilities like buildings, structures, vehicles, furniture, etc must be properly managed by the human resource manager that possesses leadership character, he has to be prudent and encourage those expected to use this facility to handle them with care, in order to extend their life span. Agu (2007) noted that the availability of these facilities in schools has a positive effect on the performance of students and Udoh in Ebong and Asodike (2016) also asserted that children will learn more and work harder when the facilities are adequately supplied.

Educational Managers and Utilization of Financial Resources

The educational system cannot be managed effectively without fund. Funding is the provision of financial resource in order to meet a need, project or programme. Money is needed to run a project or programme from within or outside the school (Ololube, 2017).

Money in the educational system is used to provide development and maintenance of the entire school system. Money as educational financial resources in Nigeria education has largely been the responsibility of the Federal, State and Local Government. They mainly fund our educational system and make money available for recurrent and capital expenditure of the various boards that constitute the ministry of education.

Recurrent expenditure refers to salaries and allowance of workers, transport expenses, maintenance of offices, hostels and feeding of students. While capital expenditures are money used in building classrooms, students' hostels, staff quarters, providing equipment and teaching aids. The resources money is

to be used by educational leaders to organize staff training, provision of libraries, building new structures and funding the specialized program . The functions of the managers are to utilize the money in educational institutions and update the schools in providing research opportunities, planning and new ideas to meet current trends in the advancement of education.

Ekunday and Ajayi (2009) defined a financial resource as a very important resource needed in the educational system and need to be well managed as a vital element in school. Educational managers must show integrity and accountability in the management of fund received in school and show evidence of receipt and payment of all that come into the school purse. This resource sometimes comes from various sources in order to develop educational sectors in Nigeria and it will only take reliable managers to manage all the money allocated to education and make them useful and valuable for the students to consume. It takes one with vision to manage school and ensures it runs as stated in schools' goals. Also, school managers should manage the monies that come into the school system, such as grants by the government and sometimes from nongovernmental organization (NGOs), such as sales, levies, endowment funds from Alumni, Philanthropists, Parent Teacher Association, etc. which are hardly adequate for effective management of education etcetera (Ebong, 2006).

Fund refers to a sum of money saved or made available for a particular purpose. It could be called money or financial resources. The fund takes any of these forms: Physical cash, credit facilities, short term fund, and external source jurisdiction. The various sources of educational financial resources are: Budgetary allocation by Government students' school fees, Endowment fund/Donations, Companies and non-governmental organizations, Industrial Training Fund, Sales and Services, Alumni Association and Aids, The host community and Parents-Teachers Association (PTA):

Educational Managers and Utilization of Time Resources: The time resources are unique by nature and very important in educational settings. Time resource has been looked down by many people. It is intangible but used to achieve all educational goals. To Ebong (2011), time is an economic phenomenon that cuts across all disciplines and occurs in every sphere of life. Yusuf and Soyemi (2012) also observed that time is a quality of nature which keeps events from happening all at once. In educational activities, the academic and non-academic programmes must be organized by the school manager or student's body and educational agencies both within and outside the school environment which is geared towards the attainment of educational goals. The time resource ironically, waits for no other resources, but others make use of it, and that is what makes it unique. It works in hours, days, weeks, months and years. Time resources walk for better output in the life of the students in educational institutions. School calendar and timetable provide programme details for each academic session. Time resource serves the purpose for which they are engaged. Educational leaders have to ensure that both learners and all categories of staff within his control use time allocated for the purpose it is meant for, knowing that anyone lost cannot be regained, most importantly on the academic environment.

Nwogu and Maduagwu (2006) saw time resource as a systematic allocation of time for all activity and strictly keep to the schedules, as achieving educational set goals. Time is constant and must be managed if planned very well to meet up slated objectives. Again, leaders can be friendly with the resources time if he/she has the ability to understand the basic skills on time planning and define period perspective. Leadership in schools require proper placement of the resources time if they must achieve result and productivity. Then time will be allocated to teachers and task them according to the level of importance and ensures it improves educational programmes effectively. However, school leaders can also develop techniques for upgrading time management in education, initially the resource time focuses at managers but presently the request of modern present-day organizational life are willing that many people, students, teachers, administrators have become interested in changing the way of working with regards to time to be

able to meet up with their future issues ahead (Ebong & Asodike, 2016). The time resources time is also used deliberately to set up work goals and personal goals in order to select major tasks and activities in educational leadership.

Kaegon (2011) opined that the time resources are used by people to plan in one hour blocks per day, while others divide the day into fifteen minutes blocks university leadership allocate time to academic and administrative members, for teaching, research and services to the institution and professional development and the community improvement. To what level which these academic and administrative staffs are expected to achieve these goals and objectives depend on the resource time as allowed by the leadership of the school. Nevertheless, teachers should note that time is so important in the educational system considering that the resources time is the only resource whenever lost, cannot be retrieved or replaced especially with the high level of unemployment in the society today, such staff can be immediately replaced, Also the resources money can be sourced from any avenues for the running of a school but when it comes to the resource time, the situation becomes difficult to replace time lost. Every school activities are carried out within a specified time; there is time for morning assembly in school, time for prep, time for classes and breaks, time for holidays, time for staff meetings, time for social activities and so on. The education managers also make use of this time in carrying out their daily task like planning, directing, implementing plans, attending meetings etc. as they recognize it as a resource and use the best approaches through which it can be best managed as they others make use of this resources called time. Elechi (2004) asserted that time management as an effective and efficient utilization of managers' corporate time to achieve educational or personal objectives. Every school manager look forward to achieving educational development making use of time and when not achieve within that particular period, might not be done again for that day because other activities are also waiting for time.

Education Resource Utilization

The term education resources have gained popularization among educators and international designers, popularizing the idea that digital materials can be designed to allow easy reuse in a wide range of teaching and learning situations (Hysten, 2007). Educational resources are sources through which institutional benefits are produced (Nwabueze in Ebong et al., 2016). Educational resource as stated by Ezeoka (2009) is anything that aids, stimulates and simplifies the learning process in the classroom. Also, Ololube (2017) perceived educational resources as the sources you use to educate yourself.

Generally, resources refer to all material items and human elements that are factored in the school business enterprise. The material resources are the capital and assets or stocks, which can be drawn upon. Okpe (2010) perceives education resources as things which satisfy the school's wants and their livelihood. These resources are the classrooms, libraries, hostels and learning revolve. They are visible (open) items in physical forms.

In view of the above definitions, educational resources can be said to be sources used in impacting and getting knowledge. These resources include instructional materials (maps, books, diagrams, charts, etc) individuals (staff) teaching and non-teaching and assets (school plants) that are transformed to produce educational benefits (Nwabuze in Ebong & Asodike, 2016).

Various sectional interests tend to perceive education resources in a restricted sense. An audiovisual enthusiast might think of resources as audiovisual equipment and complimentary staff; educational technologies in terms of the individual role of supply of information. However, on the whole, education resources are all materials available to any school or educational institution, which are meant to enhance teaching and learning (Camilleri et al., 2014). Schools which possess these resources can use them for

immediate production and alternatively for the production of further resources especially in reaching decisions during resources allocation.

Enoahowo (1990) recommended that the offices of school principals, vice-principals, as well as school staff-rooms, should be equipped and furnished with resources. A typical school should have clerical offices, stores, standard games and recreational resources. Besides, there should be standard football/soccer ground, and netball, volleyball, tennis and basket courts in schools. There may not necessarily be hard-courts or hard tarmac surfaces, rather cheaper forms using hard laterite soil can be improvised as long as there is provision for the regular watering of their surfaces (Enoahwo & Eferakeya, 1989). This suggests that an academic environment that is lacking in resource provisions and availability may not appeal or motivate the teachers and the students in the teaching-learning process. Any committed teacher or student will definitely not want to be in such a school, especially in this era when games and sports attract a very high premium in the world.

The utilization of education resources brings fruitful learning outcomes since resources stimulate students learning as well as motivating them. Human, material and financial resources are scarce; there is a need for these resources to be optimally utilized for the achievement and the implementation of education goals. There is need therefore to maximally utilize the available resources, especially now that most developing countries are faced with economic crisis to avoid wastage. Agabi (2010) perceived that in most parts of Nigeria, there are no structures or halls to house the basic types of equipment and materials for learning, which makes it possible for this equipment to be effectively utilized. Worthy of note, too, is the issue of proper management and utilization of the available teaching personnel in the school. This is one major area in which school administrators have to exhibit their managerial function by ensuring that teachers are neither over-utilized nor under-utilized.

Edem (1982) explained that the school leadership has the complex task of utilizing and directing the behaviours of the human resources towards the accomplishment of the schools' goals. This onerous task of the school leader should be extended to the extra circular activities of the school. Edem (1982) perceived that the leaders of school must also plan the school duties to be done and assign them to the teachers with the skill and training to do them. For the assignment to be fruitful, the leaders must prepare to plan to contain what each teaching post involves and the qualification that its holder requires. This contains the description of the work involved in teaching as well as extra duties. The utilization of school facilities must identify four basic techniques which can be used to cope with the shortage of school accommodation, equipment and teacher supply that characterize most developing states or countries.

Educational Managers and Method for Enforcing Discipline for Effective Utilization of Educational Resources

Clear rules and regulations should be written out by the school authority and be made known to all human resources in the educational system. The document should be served as a guide to offences and specific punishment(s) for offenders. Each rule and regulations are accompanied by their consequences. This will make both teachers and students learn to pattern their behaviour rightly. Rewards and punishment should be used to promote and sustain respectively. In using punishment, the school leadership must apply the principles of relevance, fairness, consistency and immediate action be observed. The use of corporal punishment where necessary should be used occasionally and it should be necessary to whom such powers are delegated to as well as following due process Aladeseye (2017). Punishment books detailing information about the offences and punishment given, date administered, venue and signature of the principal officer in charge must be available in school and well kept.

More so, these factors can be utilized by school managers to excel in disciplinary matters in the development of human resources. Educational leaders should imbibe the following principle:

- Must lead by example
- Must be on top of the situation,
- Must have job satisfaction,
- Must demonstrate high level of efficiency and focus on control,
- Must be committed to the career or profession,
- Must be committed to the institution or employer,
- Must have emotional stability,
- Must take responsibility and allow others to follow,
- Must be able to integrate diverse views at work helping others to exert positive influence; and
- Must have the ability to create vision at work helping others to exert positive influence.

Finally, the school leadership can utilize the services of religious bodies to focus attention on the menace of indiscipline in their sermon.

CHALLENGES IN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCE UTILIZATION

The educational resource has experienced a lot of challenges by the managers of schools:

Misuse of the school facilities: The school personnel could misuse the physical and material facilities in the school either intentionally, ignorantly or due to lack of use or overuse of school facilities due to improper planning. Most times in our present-day education whereby standard, unqualified teachers have been employed by the state and federal government to teach in our government schools and if this kind of human resource is left to handle any facilities in or to guide students on the uses, they may end up misusing such equipment or chemical as such teach cannot give what he/she doesn't have.

Poor Management: Some school managers is not left out from poor management acts and corrupt attitude as regards fund allocated to their institutions. The tendency and urge to become rich most time lead to such practice pilfering of school facilities, lack of maintenance and proper inventory are all managerial problems associated with the availability and utilization of educational resources.

Ineffective School Leadership: Some school administrators lack the capacity to command absolute managerial responsiveness from their subordinates due to inexperience. Such manager permits subordinates to do what they choose encouraging unprofessional conducts in the school. The leadership style does not emphasize discipline as such no one is held liable for damage to school properties.

Supply of Sub-standard educational resources: Corruption in the nation generally have also eaten deep into most educational managers, as they also allow and approve the supply of sub-standard educational resources in school which hardly withstand the taste of the time for uses. These resources are usually not effective to facilitate the teaching process because they are easily damaged.

Inadequate Facilities: School facilities are all education materials that facilitate effective teaching and learning in schools. The conditions of infrastructural devalue in many schools in Nigeria is an indication of

poor funding of the system. Ahmed (2003) revealed that in most of the government schools the environment are not conducive for learning and lacking the basic materials and thus hindered the objectives and goals of educational development.

In 2010 in Rivers State, Nigeria, some model schools were built without considering the students population and land space especially in urban cities and this new development ended up that 70% of the students and sent out to the caravans and community hall where they sit down on the floor to learn because the 14 classrooms built by the state government could not accommodate them, in some communities, yet it was approved by an educational managers. All the sports equipment were not standard and lack maintenance and the computers purchased were not functioning.

Political Issue: Politician has taken over resources allocated to education and thus their interests were not directed towards the system. This had resulted in inefficiency in the system. The quality and quantity of resource allowed to incumbent political leaders have towards the system. Over the years the appointment of who lead school system is done on party members. The position of educational secretary principals, board chairman, vice-chancellor, provost, dean of faculty, Head of Department, Commission for education etc. is politically appointed. Consideration of what such individual study are not put in place and this has actually made the educational system suffer.

Shortage of funds: At all levels of education funding has always been insufficient and have created a very big gap between the expected level and the actual attainment. Fund in the school system is used purchases, securing and maintenance of other educational resources, hence the poor supply of fund makes school production suffers. Money is needed to hire expiate to buy pieces of equipment that will aid learning, to build more structure that will accommodate learning and teaching. Any nations that have developed in the education sector have been closely linked with the availability of the resource fund.

Money is the life-wire for the management of the school and that is the reason United Nation Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) recommended that 26% of the national annual budget should be set aside for the management of educational sectors (Odia & Omofonmwan, 2007).

Infrastructural decay: Infrastructures is a term used to refer to products, services and facilities that are needed for an institution to function, it, therefore, means the ability of the school system to achieve her aim through the aid of infrastructure which is so important for learning Eseyin (2014) observed the roles of infrastructure play's in provision of quality education in the nation, they aid transmission of knowledge, therefore educational leader must take good care to ensure these facilities are put in place and maintained.

Lack of accountability: Accountability in education means reportage of fund and material resource with the educational system. Educational leaders having the ability to effectively account for one's performance on any given assignment or responsibility. Having the ability to fill back the public or show evidence of activities carried out in school. It takes a transparent manager to be answerable for record-keeping of revenue and expenditure of a school, reporting the educational performance of students and ability of teachers within his/her country and accounting for physical facilities within the school.

EDUCATIONAL MANAGER AND ITS ROLES IN THE UTILIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

An educational manager occupies the administrative and management position of any school settings. As acknowledged by many experts in school administration, no one else influences the whole school operation more than the manager of such level. The Head Master or Mistress, Principal, Administrator, Provost or Vice-Chancellor, Administrative Head or Manager, Community Public Relations officer, Supervisor, Instructional Leader, Curriculum Innovator, etc. are all catalyst towards planned revolution. Educational managers plan, coordinate, control, organizes and supervise the affairs of the school so that it runs smoothly. The level of administrative services provided in the school shows the quality of teaching and the importance of educational resource utilization.

Ikediugwu (2017) opined that student's performance, teachers' effectiveness and school achievement all depends on the quality of educational resources utilization provided by the school managers. The level of administrative services provided in the school shows the quality of teaching and the importance of educational resource utilization as an implication for educational managers There is no amount of learning and teaching without educational resource and utilization that can make up for lack of effective leadership. Facilities used for learning, and teaching, time allocated for learning and teaching, funds for the purchase of educational aids all lie on his or her direction or control. An effective manager assigns responsibility to subordinate, in school allocate of subjects or courses to his academic and non-academic staff according to their discipline or areas of specialization.

BENEFITS OF EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL RESOURCE

The administrative effectiveness of any school head is to effectually carry out their duties based on the following:

Managing human resource and interpersonal Relationship: Human resource utilization is concerned with people at work and their relationship within the school system. The effectiveness of education managers in this area will lead to the attainment of the teaching and learning goals of the school system. Therefore, the following are required by educational managers to effective harness human resources:

- Proper decision making ;
- Institutional maintenance and strategies for handling conflict;
- Relationship with subordinates;
- Problem solving techniques;
- The strength of motivation and morale of staff and students;
- The success of their training and development and
- The creation of a school environment in which staff and students work willingly and effectively.

Managing school finance and physical resources: School managers are expected to supervise an utilize all financial and physical resources of the school because he/she is the chief accounting officer of the school. The fundamental functions of the managers in school finance are:

- Judicious utilization of available funds for excellent carrying out of school activities
- How to raise money for educational resource utilization
- Proper financial control of available resources

- How well the available are funds effectively utilized

Managing and utilization of instructional programme: Instructional programmes are necessary for the promotion growth for students learning Babalola (2006). He should always strive for excellence in learning and teaching with the aim of improving students' academic achievement. The other roles are:

- Ensuring adequate and comprehensive supervision of all activities in school;
- Introduce innovation and change in teaching and learning;
- Encouraging best practices in teaching and learning; and
- Being able to design, implement and evaluate changes in the instructional programme of the school.

Also, educational leaders can use these procedures for achieving effective utilization of educational resources in schools. Establishing the goals and objectives he wants to achieve through the utilization of educational resource as the head of the school. The setting of objectives for the utilization of educational resource are done through:

- Creation of conducive environment for learning and teaching using human resources in school. Provision of basic facilities with the help of financial resources to enhance teaching and learning;
- Proper utilization of school staffs' and student's effectiveness;
- Utilization of a combination of good leadership skills;
- Utilization of human resource available for organizing and monitoring school activities for effectiveness; Achieving the twelve task areas, with educational resource utilization; and
- Using the human resources in the school to achieve excellence and disciplined society (Ikediugwu, 2017).

QUALITIES OF EDUCATIONAL MANAGERS

Education is a process of changing one's behaviour in order to be useful to himself and society. The behaviour could be thinking, feeling and overt actions. This implies that educational objectives and philosophy should represent the intended changes in behaviour expected from the learner. And to meet the needs of the society today educational leader is expected to utilize all the educational resources to achieve the desired needs of the society as they put up these characters and lead by examples. The basis of good leadership is a strong character and selfless devotion to an organization despite the many diverse styles of leadership, a good or effective manager inspires, motivates, and directs activities to help achieve group or organizational goals. Conversely, an ineffective managers does not contribute to organizational progress and can, in fact, detract from organizational goal accomplishment.

Accountability refers to answerability for one's actions. These actions reflect a commitment to leadership integrity. Accountability is a core quality of leaders; it helps them remain secure, predictable and stable in the course of carrying out their duties. Enaohwo and Eferakeya (1989) postulated that accountability is necessitated on grounds that the educational system has been unable to produce results that are commensurate with the vast amount of resource made available to this sector and the performance to goal attainment. The above definition of accountability, therefore, shows that schools managers are unable to give account or state clearly the amounts of money received and generated within the school environment, and state the performance of school goals.

Accountability does not only mean measurement of money and products, but it also calls for proper definition within the school system who is responsible for whom and for what. Put directly, in education (schools) management, accountability should manifest in form of products (student).

A critical review of accountability shows that many people feel threatened by the idea of accountability even more disturbed by the way the concept is being translated into action. A leader should be accountable for money and business which includes preparation of school budget, accounting for all the money received and generated from government, Parent-Teacher Association (PTA), external aids, government grants, admission fees, registration of external examination, Alumni, industrial firms, proceeds of school activities, environmental fee, endowment funds, community efforts, school fees, donations from individuals and charitable organizations, and government agencies petroleum special Trust Funds, Niger Delta Development Company (NDDC), and non- governmental organizations(NGOs). Other attributes educational leaders should imbibe for effective utilization of education resources are; honesty, integrity, competence, prudence and strong will.

CONCLUSION

Effective utilization of educational resources has always been regarded as an essential and integral part of school management and basically geared towards the enhancement of all other factors in teaching and learning process thus ensuring quality service delivery by the school to the society which determines how effective the school system is. The success of schools depends among others on effective school administration with good manager, proper time management in the school system, allocation of ample financial resources to schools, regular training and re-training of human resources in the school, perfect interrelationship with the community and ingenious utilization of the available resources in the school system.

Suggestions

- Government should organize seminars to equip school managers with the current techniques for managing school resources.
- School manager should be trained on the principles and practice of education for in-depth knowledge of effective resource management and efficient utilization of school resources for goal attainment.
- school managers should ensure that educational resources are not under-utilized but are maximized for attainment of educational goals.

REFERENCES

- Adieme, F. G., & Asodike, J. D. (2014). Theories and models of Human Resource Management. Pearl Publishers.
- Agabi, C. O. (2010). Prudential Approach to Resource Management in Nigeria Education: A theoretical perspective. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 3(2), 9-106.
- Agu, P. A. (2007). Provision of infrastructure for quality control in secondary schools in Nigeria.
- Ahmed, T. M. (2003). Education and national development in Nigeria. *Journal of studies in Education*, 10, 35-46.
- Aladeseye, A. A. (2017). Discipline as a tool for effective performance in schools. *Journal of ANCOPSS National*, 15(1).
- Babalola, J. B. (2006). *Educational Management: Thoughts and practice*. Stepson Publishing House.

- Bratton, J., & Gold, J. (2012). *Human Resource Management: Theory and practice* (5th Ed.). Palgrave
- Camilleri, A. E., Ehlers, U., & Pawlowski, J. (2014). State of art review of quality issues related to open educational resources (OER). Publications Office of the European Union.
- Chuz-Nyeche, A. (2014). Information Communication Management in a school organization. In F. N. Obasi & J. D. Asodike (Eds.), *Educational Resources management*. Chadik Printing Press.
- Ebong, J. M. (2006). *Understanding Economics of education*. Eagle lithgraph.
- Ebong, J. M. (2011). Timing the work, watching the time: The key to productivity, inaugural lecture Series. University of Port Harcourt, No. 82.
- Ebong, J. M. Asodike, A. D., & Izuagba, J. N. (2016). *Economics of Education: Expository issues*. Eagle lithograph.
- Ebong, M. J., & Asodike, D. J. (2016). *Economics of education trends in Nigeria*. Eagle lithograph.
- Edem, D. A. (1982). Introduction to Educational Administration in Nigeria. Macmillan Press.
- Ekunday, H. Z., & Ajayi, I. A. (2009). *Towards effective management of university education in Nigeria*. <http://www.codewit.com>.
- Elechi, G. E. (2004). Academic freedom and accountability: A conceptual analysis of the social demand dimension. *Nigerian Journal for Education Philosophy*, 2(11).
- Enaohwo, J. O. (1990). *Economics of Education and planning challenge*. Ammol Publication. In J. O. Enuohwo, & K Eferakeya (1989). University of Port Harcourt, *Basic Book in Educational Administration*. Paper Back Publishers.
- Enaohwo, J. O., & Eferakeya, O. A. (1989). *Educational Administration*. Paperback Publishers.
- Eseyin, E. O., Okafor, E. U., & Uchendu, E. E. (2014). Woman Education and sustainable economic development in Nigeria: *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(16), 194-199.
- Ezekoka, G. K. (2009). *Foundations of educational technology*. House of Excellence Venture.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *National Policy on Education* (Revised), NERDC press.
- Hylan, J. (2007). *Giving knowledge for free: The emergence of open educational resources*. OECD Publishing.
- Ikediugwu, N. (2017). Economic challenges in Nigeria: Implications for effective school administration and goal attainment. *Journal of ANCOSS National*, 15(1).
- Kaegon, L. (2011). Resource management in schools. In O. E Olawolu & C. U Madumere-Obike (Eds.), *Introduction: Education management practices*. Infomedia Grafixorigwe
- National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN, 2009). *Principles of institutional administration*. Gold' Sprints.
- Nwabueze, A. I. (2016). Resources in education. In Ebong, M. J. Asodike, D. J. & Izuagba J. N. *Economics of education: Expository Issues*. Eagle lithograph Publisher.
- Nwogu, U. J., & Maduagwu, S. N. (2006). *Resource Allocation and management in Education*.
- Obasi, F. N., & Asodike, J. (2007). *Resource Management in Nigerian Schools*. Alphabet Nigerian Publishers.
- Odia, L. O., & Omofonmwan, S. (2007). Educational system in Nigeria; Problems and prospects *journal of social sciences* 14(1), 81-86.
- Okpe, N. F. (2010). *Resources provision and utilization for quality public and private secondary education in Rivers State*. unpublished. Ed Thesis, National Open University of Nigeria, Lagos.
- Ololube, N. P. (2017). *Educational management, planning and supervision: model for effective implementation* (2nd Edition). Pearl Publishers.
- Ugwulashi, C. S. (2012). Time management and school administration in Nigeria: problems and prospects, Proceedings of the 1st international technology, education and environment conference(c) African Society for Scientific Research (ASSR).

- Usman, Y. D. (2016). Educational resources: an integral component for effective school administration in Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 6(13).
- Yusuf, M. A., & Soyemi, J. (2012). Achieving sustainable economic development in Nigeria through technical and vocational education and training. the missing links. *International Journal Academy Research in Business and Social Science*, 2(2), 71-77.